

MODERN APPROACHES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10057108>

Annotation. The article is discussed about knowledge, vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation in the process of language teaching. It also deals with the problems of modern approaches in language teaching.

Key words: innovation, method, technology, speech exercise, game, method, creative search game.

The future of every society depends on its development and attention to the education system, which is an integral part and vital necessity. Today, reforming and improving the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies to it, and increasing the effectiveness of education is at the level of state policy was raised.

The development of pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies created opportunities for each person to strengthen their professional training and skills. Today, innovative pedagogical technologies and interactive methods are widely used in education, especially in language and literature teaching is being used [1].

In the process of language teaching, the correct formation of knowledge, lexical, grammatical and pronunciation concepts, the correct content of the skill of self-control of the knowledge system in the minds of students is a component of innovative pedagogical technologies. Currently, the most effective teaching methods in the educational process, which are guaranteed to achieve the goals set by teachers and pedagogues. Such teaching methods, which form the ability of students to think freely, make independent decisions, solve their problems, and get out of various situations without difficulty which are the most advanced features of pedagogical technology [2].

In particular, language teaching can be done using a number of methods. The results of language teaching are determined primarily through the system of exercises, because the practical goal of language learning, that is, mastering all types of speech activity, is carried out with the help of exercises. Exercise means separate or sequential operations aimed at mastering a certain activity or improving this activity in educational processes, or it should be adequate, that is,

suitable for skills. We can see different classifications of exercises in methodological literature. It is based on different principles. For example: according to the principle of communicativeness, we can distinguish 3 types of exercises:

It is known that artistic language is the basis of any artistic work. Writing language with the help of which he creates an image of a certain person, a certain time, period. The events in the work become an image space through the inner world and psyche of the hero-man. "Thus, for a writer in a novel, the main criterion is to describe the appearance of the inner world - the experiences of the soul in the external appearance, state and behavior, that is, the dynamic principle" [5].

Before defining the concept of translation competence in this research work, we need to know what the word competence itself means. Therefore, we will dwell on what this word means. Summarizing the many definitions given, we came to the following conclusion when interpreting these concepts: "Competence" - activity in a certain field effective use of essential qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of management, and "competence" is an existing and possible ability to perform a specific activity.

The concept of "competent approach" to education at the beginning of the 21st century

became popular in the process of discussions about the problems and ways of modernization. The issue of a competent approach to the educational process in Russian linguistics was first studied by many scientists such as I. Zimnaya, A. Khutorsky, B. Elkonin and it is forbidden to effectively differentiate a specialist with competence in their work from a qualified specialist not only by having a certain level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also by being able to use them in work and effectively use them. A competent approach is a combination of general principles of setting educational goals, choosing educational content, organizing the educational process, and evaluating educational results [3].

According to the definition of O. Permyakov, competence is a description of the qualities of a person, generalized to work in certain fields as a result of training a graduate of a professional educational institution. In his opinion, "competence-activity reflects the ability, knowledge, skills and qualifications of the subject in an integral way and shows his readiness to perform functions within a certain type of activity".

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, new interactive methods have been created for the formation of translation competence in B1 level students. One of the urgent problems in the training of new personnel is the training of personnel with competent skills. To achieve this result, we rely on new technology, methods and new methods of teaching in the educational process. Students from around the world in the 2011-2020 educational process should have the following competencies:

1. To demonstrate knowledge and skills for the Motherland, relying on one's strength and knowledge;
2. Making decisions based on self-reliance;
3. Broad use of technological and information knowledge;
4. Be ready for oral and written communication;
5. To be ready for future social cooperation;
6. To be ready for self-development and advancement.

Teachers today also rely on new interactive methods to train future personnel and mature specialists. Mature specialists should not only have a perfect knowledge of the language, but also computer science, scientific and practical work and its analysis. That's why I work as a teacher in the process, they teach using their pedagogical manuals and interactive methods [4].

Because our country has chosen a democratic path, we are students lately we are using interactive methods. Although these interactive methods look easy, they are very complex and not so easy to use. That is why, in order for students to acquire such competencies, we teachers provide them with a module in the process of forming translation competence that we need to teach using technology and interactive methods.

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